

FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH BENEFITS CONTRACT WORKER INFORMATION SYSTEM (SIJAK) PT KPI RU V BALIKPAPAN WITH HOT-FIT METHOD

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Abstract

Background: It is important to acquire technology-based utilization in the inspection and verification of documents and worker's health. Additionally, some companies are transforming their service patterns and database storage. PT Kilang Pertamina International Refinery Unit V Balikpapan (PT KPI RU V Balikpapan) has a system called SIJAK. SIJAK is an information system used for registering contract workers who will work within PT KPI RU V Balikpapan. Evaluating information systems is also a practical effort to determine the actual condition of the information system. The HOT Fit Method can be used as an evaluation method for information systems. Objective: The objective of this research is to analyze the factors related to the benefits of using the Contract Worker's Information System (SIJAK) at PT KPI RU V Balikpapan using the HOT Fit method. Method: This study is analytical with a quantitative approach. The total number of respondents in the study was 100. The data collection method used in this research was a questionnaire. The data processing used Bivariate Analysis with the Chi-Square test and Multivariate Analysis with Multiple Logistic Regression. Results: This study found that the organizational structure is the most related factor to the benefits of using SIJAK at PT KPI RU V Balikpapan, with a P-value of $0.000 < 0.05$, indicating the most significant relationship to benefits or net benefits. Meanwhile, the least related factor to the benefits of using SIJAK at PT KPI RU V Balikpapan is user satisfaction, with a P-value of $0.040 < 0.05$. Conclusion: Based on the study results, the Organizational Structure variable is the most related to the benefits of using the Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK) at PT KPI RU V Balikpapan.

INTRODUCTION

The changes of workforce system is one that been shifted from a conventional system to digitalization using Internet network. Since last decade, the development of the Internet has experienced a very significant increases and rapidly growing in our society. About 3,7 billion internet users in the world in 2017, then in December 2018 it increased to 4,1 billion users. The increasing of internet users in society also directly proportional to the increasing of Information Technology that develops and became an inseparable part of societies. . [1][2]

PT Kilang Pertamina International Refinery Unit V Balikpapan (PT KPI RU V Balikpapan) has a system called SIJAK. The Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK) application been used to create contract data along with contract worker data by vendors that can be accessed outside Pertamina base network systems. SIJAK itself has been used as a platform to facilitate the vendors to verified the workers

contract data who will work in the Refinery since 2022. More than 20,000 workers were registered in this system as of 2022 [3]

One of SIJAK components were included in the Health Information System (HIS), is likely to require a rigorous evaluation that addresses technological, human and organization issues. Our review shows that current evaluation methods to evaluate various aspects of HIS and that they can still be improved. Information system evaluation is also a practical attempt to determine the actual stat of the information system. The Implementation of the HOT Fit method can be used as an information evaluation method. According to the theory of Yusof et al. (2006) a new framework that we can be used to evaluate information system, called the Human-Organization-Technology (HOT Fit) framework, is provided. HOT Fit is a combination of DeLone and McLean’s Information success model and Morton’s IT Organization Fit Model. The HOT Fit theory was proposed by Yusof et al (2006) at the 39th Hawaii Science and measures also provides technological, human and organizational Fit and Net Benefit [4] [5]

Based on author statements and data that been explained, author is interested in conducting research on Factors Related To The Benefits Of The Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK) at PT KPI RU V Balikpapan Using The HOT-Fit Method.

METHOD

This research is quantitative research and used analytical observational with a cross sectional study approach, the sample in this study is 100 samples in total admins of companies vendor who actively use the Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK). Sampling method is using saturated sample technique where the whole population is sampled, Chi-Square test were used to processing the questionnaire instrument data.

The questionnaire consist of 9 sub-statements based on the variables studied from Human factors (System Usage, User Satisfaction), Organization (Organizational Structure and Environment), Technology (System Quality and Information Quality) and Benefit or Net Benefit to the use of Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK) at PT KPI RU V Balikpapan. This research has obtained ethical approval with Number: 1698/UN4.14.1/TP.01..02/2024, before data collection is conducted, the author ask for respondents consents. After obtaining approval, the author collected questionnaire data based on respondents answers on the Google Form that had been distributed. Data processing using IBM SPSS Statistics 22 using the Chi Square test then continued with multivariate analysis of multiple logistic regression.

RESULTS

The general characteristics of respondents include age group, gender, latest education, length of service, length of use of SIJAK respondents can be seen in the following table.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondent Characteristics at PT KPI RU V Balikpapan Year 2024

Characteristics	Frequency (n=100)	Percent (%)
Age		
24-35 Years	79	79.0
36-46 Years	20	20.0
≥ 51 Years	1	1.0

Gender		
Male	42	42.0
Female	58	58.0
Last Education		
High School/ Equivalent	13	13.0
Higher Education	87	87.0
Length of Service		
<1 year	5	5.0
1-5 Years	82	82.0
6-10 Years	9	9.0
>10 Years	4	4.0
Length of Use		
<1 year	27	27.0
1-3 Years	68	68.0
4-5 Years	5	5.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 1. Shows that the most research subjects are female, namely 58 people (58.0%). Based on the age of the respondents studied, more in the age group 24-35 years, in total 79 people (79.0%). Based on the education of respondents with a higher education level, namely 87 people (87.0%).

Based on the working period of the respondents studied, more respondents with a working period of 1-5 years are 82 people (82.0%) and based on the length of use of the respondents studied, more respondents with a length of use of 1-3 years are 68 people (68.0%).

Table 2: Distribution of respondents based on the variables studied at PT KPI RU V Balikpapan Year 2024

Variable	Frequency (n = 81)	Percent (%)
<i>Benefit or Net Benefit</i>		
Good	73	73.0
Less Good	27	27.0
<i>System Usage</i>		
Good	73	73.0
Not so good	27	27.0
<i>User Satisfaction</i>		
Satisfied	66	66.0
Less Satisfied	34	34.0
<i>Organization Structure</i>		
Good	74	74.0
Not so good	26	26.0
<i>IT staff skills</i>		
Good	73	73.0
Not so good	27	27.0
<i>System Quality</i>		
Good	77	77.0
Not so good	23	23.0
<i>Information Quality</i>		
Good	62	62.0
Not so good	38	38.0
<i>Service Quality</i>		
Good	72	72.0
Not so good	28	28.0
Total	81	100.0

Table 2. shows that most of the respondents get benefit from the use of SIJAK at PT KPI RU V Balikpapan (73.0%). Most of the system usage is good (73.0%) and the average satisfaction with the use of SIJAK is (66.0%) in terms of organizational structure is good (74.0%), in terms of IT staff capability (73.0%), SIJAK system quality is good (73.0%). SIJAK information quality is good (62.0%) and SIJAK service quality is also good (72.0%).

Table 3: Bivariate Analysis of Factors Associated with Benefits of Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK) PT KPI RU V Balikpapan with HOT-Fit Method

Variables	Benefit or Net Benefit				Total		P Value
	Good		Not so good		n	%	
	n	%	n	%			
System Usage							
Good	58	79,5	15	20,5	73	100	0.033
Not so good	15	55,6	12	44,4	27	100	
User Satisfaction							
Satisfied	53	80,3	13	19,7	66	100	0.040
Less Satisfied	20	58,8	14	41,2	34	100	
Organization Structure							
Good	63	85,1	11	14,9	74	100	0.000
Not so good	10	38,5	16	61,5	26	100	
IT Staff Capabilities							
Good	59	80,8	14	19,2	73	100	0.008
Not so good	14	51,9	13	48,1	27	100	
System Quality							
Good	61	79,2	16	20,8	77	100	0.022
Not so good	12	52,2	11	47,8	23	100	
Information Quality							
Good	53	85,5	9	14,5	62	100	0.001
Not so good	20	52,6	18	47,4	38	100	
Service Quality							
Good	59	81,9	13	18,1	72	100	0.003
Not good	14	50,0	14	50,0	28	100	

Source: Primary Data

The results of bivariate statistical test among 7 variables on factors related to the benefits of Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK) at PT KPI RU V Balikpapan is obtained 3 variables, which is: Organizational Structure variable with P-Value= 0.000<0.05, Information Quality variable with P-Value= 0.001<0.05, Service Quality variable with P-Value=0.003<0.05 means that there is a highly significant relationship between Organizational Structure, Information Quality and Service Quality variables with Net Benefit of Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK) at PT KPI RU V Balikpapan, while IT Staff Ability variable with P-Value= 0.008<0.05, variable of System Usage with P-Value=0.033<0.05 and variable of User Satisfaction with P-Value= 0.040<0.05 means that there is still significant influence too but not as strong as others 3 variable with Benefits of Net Benefit of Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK) at PT KPI RU V Balikpapan.

Table 4: Logistic Regression Analysis of Factors Associated with Benefits of Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK) PT KPI Refinery Unit V Balikpapan Year 2024

Variables	B	Wald	Sig.	Exp(B)
System Usage	-0.140	0.027	0.869	0.870
User Satisfaction	0.305	0.156	0.693	1.357
Organization Structure	3.230	13.328	0.000	25.280
IT Staff Capabilities	2.545	9.663	0.002	12.737
System Quality	2.312	7.787	0.005	10.098
Information Quality	3.011	12.993	0.000	20.306
Service Quality	0.601	0.703	0.402	1.825

Source: Primary Data

The table above shows that out of 100 respondents, the variable that is most related among other variables is the organizational structure variable with an exp β of 25.280, which means that the organizational structure is 25 times greater than other variables so that this variable had the biggest relationship among other variables to the Benefit.

DISCUSSION

1. Relationship between System Usage and Benefits of Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK) PT KPI RU V Balikpapan

Research hypothesis 1 (H1) is accepted, meaning that there is a relationship between system usage and *net benefit* towards the use of Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK) of PT KPI RU V Balikpapan.

In the digital era, the utilization of information and communication technology has been carried out in various sectors of life. The utilization of technological advances requires an effective and productive system, one of the techniques commonly used to evaluate the implementation of existing systems in an institution is *HOT FIT* [6] Examples of evaluation steps according to the appropriate dimensions and factors are listed, where these evaluation dimensions affect each other temporally and causally, including System Usage, which relies on user knowledge and training, can affect Information Quality, because user knowledge in using the system can affect reports, images and recipes produced by the system. [7]

From the results of this study, it was found that out of 100 respondents, who had good system usage with a good benefit or net benefit category, 58 people (79.5%) stated that system usage had a relationship to benefits or *net benefits*. This is in line with Ilma Soraya's research (2019) which shows that the higher the level of use of a system, the more useful the system is for users. [8]

In the measurement aspect of HOT FIT, namely the human aspect, there are 2 aspect components, namely System Usage and User satisfaction. System usage covers the level of use (frequency, duration), use of how the system works, experience / expertise, resistance and training. From the aspect of benefits or *net benefits*. Benefits in this context are the equivalence of negative and convincing results from using information systems. So, the more convincing the results increase, the higher the application of the information composition. [9]

The level of information system utilization by SIJAK users at PT KPI RU V Balikpapan shows a high result, so the benefits obtained from system users are also high. From

the statistical test result of *P-value* $0.033 < 0.05$, system user is known to be one of the components of *Human* element which has relationship to *net benefit*. Therefore, the active use of SIJAK system in PT KPI RU V Balikpapan can give benefit or *net benefit* to the Company itself.

2. Relationship between User Satisfaction and Benefits of Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK) PT KPI RU V Balikpapan

Research hypothesis 2 (H2) is accepted, meaning that there is a relationship between user satisfaction and net benefit towards the use of Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK) of PT KPI RU V Balikpapan.

User satisfaction is the overall evaluation of the user's experience in using the information system and the potential impact of the information system. User satisfaction can be related to perceived usefulness and user attitude towards information system which are influenced by personal characteristics. ^[4] In addition, user satisfaction is a user reaction and feedback that arises after using an information system, where the user's attitude towards the information system becomes a criterion for seeing how much the user likes the implemented system. ^[10]

From the results of this study, it is found that out of 100 respondents, those who have user satisfaction are satisfied with the category of benefits or good net benefit as many as 53 people (80.3%), this states that the higher the user's satisfaction with the system, the higher users can feel the benefits from the system that can help their daily work. Based on the results of the statistical test, the P-Value is $0.040 < 0.05$, indicating a relationship between user satisfaction and the benefits of SIJAK itself, but the lowest relationship among all the variables studied. This is because it is felt that the features and functions in SIJAK are not fully in accordance with the needs in assisting daily tasks. This was also found in research conducted by Nasiatul Fanny (2019) where there are limitation from the Human component, namely that there are no workers or officers who meet the benefit of this system can simplify and ease the work of the officers themselves, although there is still some information that cannot be accessed. ^[11] ^[12]

So, the higher the level of user satisfaction with benefits or net benefits, the higher the benefits that users can feel from the system.

3. Relationship between Organizational Structure and Benefits of Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK) PT KPI RU V Balikpapan

Research hypothesis 3 (H3) is accepted, meaning that there is a relationship between Organizational Structure and Benefits or Net benefit towards the use of Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK) of PT KPI RU V Balikpapan.

According to Musrifar (2017) a good organizational structure can be seen from the management, communication and support received from the organization also we can saw other good organizational structure where they can be able to separate functional responsibilities strictly to support the success of the information system implemented.

Based on the results of this study, it is found that out of 100 respondents, those who have a good organizational structure with a good benefit or net benefit category are 63 people (85.1%), this shows that the better the organizational structure is formed, the more useful the user's encouragement to use an information system will be felt which can help coordinate between units very well, this is in line with Ani's research

(2018) which shows the influence of organizational structure on benefits. Organizational must have the ability to prepare human resources to be able to adjust to problem that may occur in implementing information system to reduce obstacles in managing transformation. ^[13] This can be achieved through strategies and management such as leader support, teamwork and effective communication formed by involving employee roles and abilities.

From all variables studied through statistical test, *P-value* $0.000 < 0.05$ is obtained, indicating a high relationship between organizational structure and benefit or net benefits, this can explain that the better and clearer the organizational structure, the better the benefits obtained from the use of SIJAK at PT KPI RU V Balikpapan. This is because communication and facility assistance from the management is considered very good so that it can help improve performance and coordination between units.

4. Relationship between IT Staff Capability and Benefits of Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK) PT KPI RU V Balikpapan

Research hypothesis 4 (H4) is accepted, meaning that there is a relationship between IT Staff Capability and Benefits or *net benefit* towards the use of Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK) of PT KPI RU V Balikpapan.

The IT Staff ability here included in the second aspect in measuring the HOT Fit model, namely organizational aspects, including structure and environment. This organizational environment is the application of applications that receive support and assistance from all work units, including IT Staff. ^[8]

Based on the results of this study, it is found that out of 100 respondents, those who have good IT staff abilities with good benefit or *net benefit* categories are 59 people (80.8%), this shows that the better the ability of IT staff to realize information systems to run well, the clearer and better the benefits will be obtained. This is in line with Lourent's research (2019), where the organizational environment has a significant influence on benefits or *net benefits*. Practically, the organization greatly influences the benefits obtained from information systems. The encouragement to communicate has a stated significant effect on benefits. Management provides support and implements the right strategy based on the conditions of the organizational environment. Other research that explains the importance of the IT staff capability component is explained by Adani, Sri et al. where an organization that has a component in it, namely IT Staff, needs to update the system regularly so that the data access response speed runs fast. ^{[14][15][16]}

According to Bayu and Izzati (2013), encouragement from the organizational environment can significantly provide motivation to improve the performance of organizational members and system providers. This can be achieved through strategies and management such as leader support, teamwork, and effective communication formed by involving employee roles and abilities. ^[1]

5. Relationship between System Quality and Benefits of Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK) PT KPI RU V Balikpapan

Research hypothesis 5 (H5) is accepted, meaning that there is a relationship between System Quality and Benefits or Net Benefit towards the use of Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK) of PT KPI RU V Balikpapan. System quality can be defined as the quality of the combination of hardware and software used in information system. ^[5] System quality is used to measure the information technology system itself,

where the quality of this system will describe the characteristics of system performance. ^[17] System quality is measured by looking at the quality of the combination of hardware and software in an information system. ^[18]

Based on the results of this study, it was found that out of 100 respondents, those who had a good system quality with a good benefit or net benefit category were 61 people (79.2%), this shows that the higher or better the quality of a system, the higher the level of benefit or net benefit of the system felt by users. The results of this study are in line with the results of research from Mangindara (2023) which states that the better the quality of the system owned, the more accurate the work results obtained from using SIMRS. ^[19]

In addition, according to the literature review from Wilis Putri Hapsari (2022) in line with this research where she explains that system quality can be measured from the features integrated in the information system itself, so that it can easily assess the relationship between users, system quality and the benefits obtained from the information system. In line with research conducted by Rizky and Maulidyati (2024) on the implementation of the HOT-Fit method for Information Systems also show that system quality plays an important role in user satisfaction so that it becomes a reference for the Information System developments. ^{[20] [21]}

6. Relationship between Information Quality and Benefits of Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK) PT KPI RU V Balikpapan

Research hypothesis 6 (H6) is accepted, meaning that there is a relationship between Information Quality and Benefit or net benefit towards the use of Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK) of PT KPI RU V Balikpapan.

Information quality shows the quality of products produced by information systems. The better the quality of information, the more it will affect the decisions made by users. According to Yusof et al (2008), the quality of information is assessed by the level of accuracy and the level of relevance of the information data. It is said to be accurate if the information is error-free and unbiased. ^[4]

Based on the results of this study, it is found that out of 100 respondents, those who have a good information quality with a good net benefit category are 53 people (85.5%), this shows that the higher or better the quality of information, the higher the benefits obtained by users of the system, this is in line with Anang's research (2021), which explains that technological factors, namely information systems, have achievements in high categories so that they will encourage high benefits or net benefits from using SIMRS. The existence of high access speed and actual technology in the presentation and delivery of information will increase the ease with which employees can access information and provide the best service. The presentation of updated data and data security will improve the delivery of complete information and the convenience of employees in working and accessing information. ^{[7] [22]}

7. Relationship between Service Quality and Benefits of Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK) PT KPI RU V Balikpapan

Research hypothesis 7 (H7) is accepted, meaning that there is a relationship between Service Quality and Benefit or net benefit towards the use of Contract Worker Information System (SIJAK) of PT KPI RU V Balikpapan. Service quality focuses on the overall support received by a system or technology service provider. Service quality can be assessed by speed of response, assurance, empathy and service

follow-up. [5] in this study, the quality of service in question is the support services obtained by information system users from information system service providers to users in this case to ensure the system is running properly.

Based on the results of this study, it is found that out of 100 respondents, those who have good service quality with good benefit or net benefit categories are 59 people (81.9%), this shows that the higher or better the quality of service of a system, the higher the level of benefit or net benefit of the information system. The results of this study are in line with Mangindara's research (2023) explaining that service quality has a relationship to benefits or net benefits, this is because a system has an important role in completing work so that IT must always be ready to handle problems with information system in order to provide quality service. [19]

8. Most related factors and more beneficial for PT KPI RU V Balikpapan based on HOT Fit Framework

Based on the result of Multivariate Analysis of Multiple Logistic Regression, it is found that out of 100 respondents, the most related variable among other variables is organizational structure variable with $\text{Exp}(B)$ of 25,280 this shown that Organizational Structure gives the most benefit and becomes a factor related to the benefit of SIJAK application in PT KPI RU V Balikpapan as an information system that facilitates users and service providers to improve performance and coordination between units, It also shows to the management of PT KPI RU V Balikpapan that one of the factors in HOT Fit assessment aspect which is Organization represented by Organizational Structure variable, has significant effect on net benefit With the result of data which has high response, the management of PT KPI RU V Balikpapan is believed to be able to optimize the benefit or net benefit which is determined considering the users of SIJAK application have felt the benefit of this application to simplify the work as shown by the table attached in the previous section.

The results obtained by researchers are in line with the research of Silvanus and Supriyantoro (2020), it is explained that the organizational structure variable has an influence which states that the importance of management's role in implementing Information System and can be concluded through the calculation of the most dominant total coefficient on system usability which comes from the organizational structure and the insignificance of the influence of organizational structure on the benefits of information systems. [23]

CONCLUSION

- 1) Based on the results of the research, the factor that is most related to the benefits or net benefits of SIJAK PT KPI RU V Balikpapan with HOT-Fit method is found to be Organization, namely the Organizational Structure variable which is most related to the benefits of using the Contra Worker Information System (SIJAK) PT KPI RU V Balikpapan due to the well-established Organizational Structure which helps improve performance and coordination between units really well.
- 2) Based on the results of the research, the lowest factor related to the benefits or net benefits of SIJAK PT KPI RU V Balikpapan with HOT Fit method is obtained Human factor, namely User Satisfaction variable with p value = $0.040 < 0.05$, however related to user satisfaction, the benefits of this Information System can simplify and ease the workload of the officer/admin vendor itself, although there is still some information that cannot be accessed.

Bibliography

- 1) Bayu and Izzati, "Evaluasi Faktor-Faktor Kesuksesan Implementasi Sistem Informasi Manajemen Rumah Sakit di PKU Muhammadiyah Sruweng dengan Menggunakan Metode HOT-Fit.," Seminar Nasional Informatika Medis (SNIMED), vol. IV, pp. 78-86, 2023.
- 2) C. Sleezer, T. Wentling and R. Cude, *Human Resource Development and Information Technology*, New York: Springer Science and Business Media, 2002.
- 3) P. P. (. Refinery Unit V, "Pertamina.com," 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://pertamina.com/Media/Upload/Files/Sustainability-Report-RU-V-2017.pdf>. [Accessed 14 July 2024].
- 4) M. M. K. J. P. A. S. L. Yusof, "An evaluation Framework for Health Information System: Human, Organization and Technology-Fit Factors (HOT-fit)," *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 2008.
- 5) M. B. Urbach N, "the Update DeLone and MCLean Model of Information System Success," *Journal of Management Information Systems*, vol. 1, pp. 1-18, 2012.
- 6) F. S. A. S. S. Y. Tawar, "Model HOT FIT dalam Manajemen Sistem Informasi," *Bincang Sains dan Teknologi (BST)*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 76-82pp, 2022.
- 7) E. Esperanza Sala and A. Pribadi Subriadi, "Hot-Fit Model to Measure the Effectiveness and Efficiency of Information System in Public Sector," *The Winners*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 131-141, 2022.
- 8) I. Soraya, "Penguujian Model HOT FIT Pada Sistem Sistem Informasi Manajemen Obat di Instalasi Farmasi RSGMP UNSOED," *Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis, Purwokerto*, 2019.
- 9) S. Hidayatullah, D. Arman Prasetya, d. Ari Purnomo and I. Kusdyah Rachmawati, *HOT FIT Model Pengembangan Sistem Informasi*, Ponorogo: Uwais Inspirasi Indonesia, 2022.
- 10) C. K Davis, *Technologies and Methodologies for Evaluating Information Technology in Business*, Houston, USA: IRM Press Publisher of Innovative scholarly and professional information technology titles in the cyberage, 2003.
- 11) N. Fanny, K. Adi and S. Patria Jati, "Penerapan Model Hot Fit pada Evaluasi Sistem Informasi Keselamatan dan Kesehatan Kerja di RSUD Dr. Moewardi," *Media Kesehatan Masyarakat Indonesia*, vol. 19, no. 1, 2020.
- 12) H. Kip, N. Beerlage-de Jong, Lisette, V. Gemert-Pijnen, R. Sanderman and S. M Kelders, *eHealth Research Theory and Development; A Multidisciplinary Approach Second Edition*, New York: Routledge, 2024.
- 13) A. Khotimah, "Evaluasi Sistem Informasi Manajemen Rumah Sakit Rajawali Citra Yogyakarta Menggunakan Model Human Organization Technology Fit (HOT-Fit)," *Journal of Information System for Public Health*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 19-26, 2018.
- 14) L. Monelizabeth E, "Implementasi Kerangka Kerja Evaluasi Human, Organization And Technology-Fit (HOT-FIT) Pada sistem Informasi Rekam Medis Elektronik (RME) di Rumah Sakit Kristen Mojowarno, Jombang," *Institut Sepuluh Nopember (ITS)*, 2019.
- 15) A. Setiorini, S. Natasia, Y. Tri Wiranti and D. Ramadhan, "Evaluation of The Application of Hospital Management Information System (SIMRS) in RSUD Dr. Kanujoso Djatiwibowo Using The HOT-Fit Method," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2021.
- 16) A. Anugrawan and Y. Rahadian, "Evaluation of Follow-Up Monitoring Information System Using Hot Fit Model," *Electronic, Control, Telecommunication, Information and Power Engineering (ECOTIPE) Journal*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 12-21, 2023.
- 17) D. Krisbiantoro, "Evaluasi Keberhasilan Implementasi Sistem Informasi Dengan Pendekatan HOT-Fit (Studi Kasus: Perpustakaan STMIK AMIKOM Purwokerto)," *Jurnal Konferensi Nasional Sistem dan Informatika*, 2015.
- 18) R. Spanò and F. Luca, *Information System in Healthcare: Current Issue and Future Trends*, United Kingdom: Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 2020.

- 19) Mangindara, S. Windarti and A. Nadya, Implementasi Sistem Informasi Manajemen Rumah Sakit (SMRS), vol. 6, Pekalongan: Penerbit NEM, 2023.
- 20) W. Putri Hapsari, U. Abdul Labib, Haryanto and D. Widya, "A Literature Review of Human, Organization, Technology (HOT)- Fit Evaluation Model," *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, Atlantis Press, vol. 541, pp. 876-880, 2021.
- 21) R. Marisa Putri and M. Aisyah, "Implementing the HOT-Fit method in Hospital Management Information Systems Evaluation," *International Conference On Accounting and Finance*, vol. 2, pp. 25-36, 2024.
- 22) A. A. F. Suryana, "Model Peningkatan Pemanfaatan Sistem Informasi Rumah Sakit Berdasarkan Metode Hot-Fit di RSPI Prof.Dr.Sulianti Saroso," *Jurnal pembangunan Manusia dan Kebudayaan*, 2021.
- 23) S. Chakra Puspita, Supriyantoro and Hasyim, "Analysis of Hospital Information System Implementation Using the Human-Organization-Technology (HOT) Fit Method: A Case Study Hospital in Indonesia," *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, vol. 5, no. 6, 2020.
- 24) T. U Daim, N. A Behkami, N. Basoglu, O. M kök and L. Hogaboam, *healthcare Technology Innovation Adoption: Electronic Health Records and Other Emerging Health Information Technology Innovations*, Poertland: Springer, 2016.
- 25) M. B.-F. P. W. Maria, "The Impact Of Online Health Information on Patient Health Behaviours and Making Decisions Concerning Health," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, p. 1, 2020.
- 26) K. L. Rasid, "PENERAPAN METODE HUMAN ORGANIZATION TECHNOLOGY AND BENEFIT (HOT Fit) UNTUK EVALUASI TINGKAT KEBERHASILAN LAYANAN SISTEM (Studi Kasus: Sistem Informasi Akademik (SIMAK) Versi 2 Universitas Khairun Ternate)," *Jurnal Jaringan dan Teknologi Informasi*, pp. 20-21, 2022.
- 27) N. A. K. Fanny, "Penerapan Model HOT Fit pada Evaluasi Sistem Informasi Keselamatan dan Kesehatan Kerja di RSUD Dr. Moewardi," Universitas Diponegoro, 2019.
- 28) Musrifah, "Implementasi Teknologi Informasi Menggunakan Human Organization Technology (HOT) Fit Model Di Perpustakaan Perguruan Tinggi," *Jurnal Ilmu Perpustakaan dan Informasi*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 71-78, 2017.
- 29) A. A. Vantissha, "Assesing Hospital Management Information System Success Using Human Organization and Technology Fit Model," *Applied Information System and Management (AIMS)*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 37-44, 2022.
- 30) M. Nur and A. A. Goldha, "IT Unit RU V Balikpapan Application Design and Work Flow," PT Kilang Pertamina Internasional Refinery Unit V Balikpapan, Balikpapan, 2022.